

Figure 5c: The 9x9 vāstu, DM 76.1-16.

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|----------------|---------------|----------------|
| 1 Brahmā | 19 Satya | 37 Pāpayakṣman |
| 2 Āryaman | 20 Bhṛṣa | 38 Roga |
| 3 Vivasvant | 21 Antarikṣa | 39 Vasuki |
| 4 Mitra | 22 Agni | 40 Mukhya |
| 5 Pṛthivīdhara | 23 Pūṣan | 41 Bhalvāṭa |
| 6 Āpa | 24 Vitatha | 42 Soma |
| 7 Āpavatsa | 25 Gṛhākṣata | 43 Ananta |
| 8 Savitṛ | 26 Yama | 44 Aditi |
| 9 Sāvitrī | 27 Gandharva | 45 Diti |
| 10 Indra | 28 Bhṛṅga | |
| 11 Indrajaya | 29 Mṛga | |
| 12 Rudra | 30 Pitṛ | |
| 13 Skanda | 31 Dvauvārika | |
| 14 Īśa | 32 Sugrīva | 46 Carakī |
| 15 Parjanya | 33 Puṣpadanta | 47 Vidārī |
| 16 Jayanta | 34 Pracetas | 48 Pūtanā |
| 17 Mahendra | 35 Asura | 49 Pāparākṣasī |
| 18 Sūrya | 36 Śoṣa | |

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49									46										
38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	14											
37	12							6	15										
36		13	5			7	16												
35								17											
34	4		1			2		18											
33								19											
32		10	3			8	20												
31	1							9	21										
30	29	28	27	26	25	24	23	22											
48									47										